

R Notebook

```
library(knitr)
# Set so that long lines in R will be wrapped:
opts_chunk$set(tidy.opts=list(width.cutoff=40),tidy=TRUE)
```

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```
library(tibble)
library(data.table)
library(InformationValue)
library(MASS)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyverse)
library(tm)

#function to print out total NAs by columns
NA_per_col<-function(df){
  for (col in 1:ncol(df)){
    n<-sum(is.na(df[,col]))
    if (n>0){
      print(paste(colnames(df[col]),n))
      "/n"
    }
  }
}

'%!in%' <- function(x,y)!('%in%'(x,y))
```

1. functions

2. **data** get csv files -for this paper, train: 2009 - 2018; test - 2019

```
train_ori<-fread("/DIN_train.csv")
test_ori<-fread("/DIN_test.csv")
```

clean up unnecessary columns -the tick/pathogen datasets for the later years may not be in the same format as earlier years or may have the additional columns. May need to do some additional cleanup such as removing punctuation, repeating columns (i.e. Date.x,Date.y), NAs, etc. Just need datasets consistent enough to merge.

```
train<-data.frame(train_ori)
test<-data.frame(test_ori)
```

```
#train df
NA_per_col(train)
train_df<-na.omit(train)
```

```
#test df
NA_per_col(test)
test_df<-na.omit(test)
```

check class of covariates

```
train_df$turkeySpring<-as.numeric(train_df$turkeySpring)
train_df$critical_binary<-factor(train_df$critical_binary)
train_df$road_class<-factor(train_df$road_class)
train_df$road_type<-factor(train_df$road_type)
train_df$ecozone_major<-factor(train_df$ecozone_major)

test_df$EncounterDistance<-as.numeric(test_df$EncounterDistance)
test_df$critical_binary<-factor(test_df$critical_binary)
test_df$road_class<-factor(test_df$road_class)
test_df$road_type<-factor(test_df$road_type)
test_df$ecozone_major<-factor(test_df$ecozone_major)
```

add proportion of infected ticks

```
train_df$prop<-train_df$BB_Pos/train_df$total_tested
test_df$prop<-test_df$BB_Pos/test_df$total_tested
```

combine train & test data

```
data_df<-dplyr::bind_rows(train_df,test_df)
```

create a dataframe of only common columns

```
cols_to_keep <- intersect(colnames(train_df),colnames(test_df))

train_for_all<-train_df[,cols_to_keep, drop=TRUE]
test_for_all<-test_df[,cols_to_keep, drop=FALSE]
df_all<-bind_rows(train_for_all,test_for_all)
```

3. analysis of collected data *map it to NYS*

```

library(ggplot2)
library(ggmap)
library(maps)
library(mapdata)
library(RColorBrewer)

usa <- map_data("state")
ny <- subset(usa, region %in% "new york")
counties<-map_data("county")
ny_county<-subset(counties, region=="new york")

ny_base <- ggplot(data = ny, mapping = aes(x = long, y = lat, group = group)) +
  coord_fixed(1.3) +
  geom_polygon(color = "black", fill = "white")

gg<-ny_base + theme_nothing(legend = TRUE)
plot(gg)

```

simplified dataframe of infection at each site

```

df_BB_w2019<-df_all[,c("LAT", "LONG", "Year", "BB_Pos", "total_tested", "prop")]
df_BB_w2019$tickPropCat<-cut(df_BB_w2019$prop,breaks=c(-.01,0,.1,.2,.3,.4,1),labels=c("0", "(0-.1]", "(.1-.2]", ".2-.3]", ".3-.4]", ".4-1]"))
df_BB.1<-df_BB

```

split counties into ecoregions https://www.dec.ny.gov/docs/wildlife_pdf/ecoregmap.pdf https://www.dec.ny.gov/docs/lands_forests_pdf/nyecoregions.pdf

```

eco1<-c("oswego", "wayne", "monroe", "orleans", "niagara", "erie", "genesee", "livingston", "ontario", "yates", "cattaraugus", "schuyler", "chemung", "tioga", "broome", "chenango", "cattaraugus", "wyoming", "allegany", "steuben", "schuyler", "chemung", "tioga", "broome", "chenango", "cattaraugus", "westchester", "rockland", "putnam", "orange", "dutchess", "columbia", "albany", "rensselaer", "saratoga", "kings", "queens", "bronx", "new york", "richmond", "nassau", "suffolk")
eco4<-c("kings", "queens", "bronx", "new york", "richmond", "nassau", "suffolk")
eco5<-c("lewis", "herkimer", "hamilton", "clinton", "essex", "warren", "franklin")
eco6<-c("st lawrence", "jefferson")
eco7<-c("chautauqua")

eco<-list(eco1,eco2,eco3,eco4,eco5,eco6,eco7)
eco_names<-c("1. great lakes", "2. high allegheny plateau", "3. lower NE/ piedmont", "4. atlantic coast", "5. adirondack park", "6. northern tier", "7. southern tier")

```

changes in infection by region

```

for(e in 1:length(eco)){
  temp_eco<-eco[[e]]
  for (c in 1:length(temp_eco)){
    df_BB.1[which(df_BB.1$County==temp_eco[c]),"ecoregion"]<-eco_names[e]
  }
}
#lm
for (div in 1:7){
  temp_df1<-df_BB.1[which(df_BB.1$ecoregion==eco_names[div]),]
  temp_p<-ggplot(temp_df1,aes(x=factor(Year),y=prop)) + geom_boxplot(aes(x=factor(Year),y=prop)) + ggtitle(eco_names[div]) +
  labs(x="Year", y="Borrelia %") + geom_smooth(method = "lm", se=TRUE, aes(group=1))
}

```

```

  plot(temp_p)
}

#all the sites together by ecoregion
df_BB.1$ecoregion<-paste0("reg_",df_BB.1$ecoregion)
group.col<-brewer.pal(7, "Dark2")

ggplot(df_BB.1, aes(y=prop, x=Year, color=ecoregion)) + geom_smooth(method="loess",se=FALSE,size=1) + t

#only ecoregions with more data points
df_BB.1$eco_num<-as.numeric(gsub(".*?([0-9]+).*", "\\1", df_BB.1$ecoregion))
ggplot(df_BB.1[which(df_BB.1$eco_num != 7 & df_BB.1$eco_num != 6 & df_BB.1$eco_num != 4),], aes(y=prop,

```

infection rate over years for 5 representative sites

```

#counties listed here but better to use locations
temp<-df_all[which(df_all$County=="Chemung" | df_all$County=="Cattaraugus" | df_all$County=="Orange" | d

#to make line plot
temp1<-temp[,c("Year","prop","County")]
temp2<-temp1 %>% group_by(Year,County) %>% summarise(med_prop=median(prop))
temp2<-data.frame(temp2)
temp2$med_prop<-temp2$med_prop * 100
ggplot(data=temp2, aes(x=Year, y=med_prop, color=County),group=FALSE) + geom_smooth(method="lm", se=FALSE)

#to map counties
ny_county1<-ny_county[which(ny_county$subregion %in% c("orange", "chemung", "onondaga", "cattaraugus", "

gg_county<-ny_base + theme_nothing(legend = TRUE) + geom_polygon(data = ny_county, fill = "white", color=
plot(gg_county)

```

4. model variable selection using 2009-2018 data

```

n<-1
train1ori<-data_df_newGIS[which(data_df_newGIS$total_tested>10),]
train1<-subset(train1ori,select=-c(Year,County,Location,total_tested, Date1, row_num, Town, Notes, Larva))

#variable selection
assign(paste0("m",n,"_full"), (glm(cbind(BB_Pos,BB_Neg) ~ ., data=get(paste0("train",n)), family=binomial))
assign(paste0("m",n,"_null"), (glm(cbind(BB_Pos,BB_Neg) ~ 1, data=get(paste0("train",n)), family=binomial))
assign(paste0("m",n), stepAIC(get(paste0("m",n,"_null")), scope=list(lower=get(paste0("m",n,"_null")),upper=get(paste0("m",n,"_full"))))
assign(paste0("m",n,"_coef"), names(coef(get(paste0("m",n))))[-1])
length(coef(get(paste0("m",n))))

summary(m1)

```

5. predictive power of model check for autocorrelation

```

par(mfrow=c(2,2))
plot(m1)

```

```
qqnorm(residuals(m1,type="deviance"))
abline(a=0,b=1)
acf(residuals(m1))
```

model in-training data analysis

```
#plot actual vs. predicted data for 2009-2018
ggplot(train1ori, aes(y=m1$fitted.values,x=prop)) + geom_point() + ggtitle("Model predictions: actual v

library(PropCIs)
acc_df<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=length(m1$fitted.values),ncol=3))
colnames(acc_df)<-c("predictions", "BB_Pos", "total_tested")
acc_df[,1]<-m1$fitted.values
acc_df[,2]<-train1ori$BB_Pos
acc_df[,3]<-train1ori$total_tested
for(row in 1:nrow(acc_df)){
  acc_df$conf_2.5[row]<-exactci(acc_df$BB_Pos[row], acc_df$total_tested[row], .95)[[1]][1]
  acc_df$conf_97.5[row]<-exactci(acc_df$BB_Pos[row], acc_df$total_tested[row], .95)[[1]][2]
  if(acc_df$predictions[row]<=acc_df$conf_97.5[row] & acc_df$predictions[row]>=acc_df$conf_2.5[row]){
    acc_df$accurate[row]<-1
  }
  if(acc_df$predictions[row]>acc_df$conf_97.5[row] | acc_df$predictions[row]<acc_df$conf_2.5[row]){
    acc_df$accurate[row]<-0
  }
}
}
#total correct
sum(acc_df$accurate)
#incorrect
length(acc_df$accurate) - sum(acc_df$accurate)
# percentage correct
sum(acc_df$accurate) / length(acc_df$accurate)

#over or under?
acc_df$inacc<-"A"
for(row in 1:nrow(acc_df)){
  if(acc_df$predictions[row] < acc_df$conf_2.5[row]){
    acc_df$inacc[row]<-"U"
  }
  if(acc_df$predictions[row] > acc_df$conf_97.5[row]){
    acc_df$inacc[row]<- "O"
  }
}
}
```

predict out-of-sample to 2019

```
#OOS to 2019 (10+ ticks)
group.colors<- c("#FFEDA0", "#FEB24C", "#FC4E2A", "#BD0026", "#800026")
temp_test_df<-test_df[which(test_df$total_tested>10),]
assign(paste0("m",n,"_pred19"),predict(get(paste0("m",n)),newdata=temp_test_df,type="response"))

#plot 2019 actual vs predicted
temp_test_df$pred<-get(paste0("m",n,"_pred19"))
temp_test_df$tickTestedCat<-cut(temp_test_df$total_tested,breaks=c(10,15,25,35,45,85),labels=c("11-15",
```

```
temp_test_df$row_num1<-1:nrow(temp_test_df)
```

```
temp_plot<-ggplot(temp_test_df, aes(y=pred,x=prop)) + geom_point(aes(color=tickTestedCat)) + scale_color_
plot(temp_plot)
```

how well did the model do when predicting out-of-sample to 2019 -determine over/underpredictions to previously visited + new sites

```
#sites visited for the first time in 2019
```

```
summary(m1_pred19 - temp_test_df$prop)
```

```
tmp<-setdiff(temp_test_df[,c("LAT", "LONG")],train1ori[,c("LAT", "LONG")])
```

```
temp_test_df[temp_test_df$LAT %in% tmp$LAT, "new"]<-"yes"
```

```
temp_test_df[temp_test_df$LAT %!in% tmp$LAT, "new"]<-"no"
```

```
#number correct and incorrect based on confidence intervals
```

```
oos_acc_df<-data.frame(matrix(nrow=nrow(temp_test_df),ncol=3))
```

```
colnames(oos_acc_df)<-c("predictions", "BB_Pos", "total_tested")
```

```
oos_acc_df[,1]<-temp_test_df$pred
```

```
oos_acc_df[,2]<-temp_test_df$BB_Pos
```

```
oos_acc_df[,3]<-temp_test_df$total_tested
```

```
for(row in 1:nrow(oos_acc_df)){
```

```
  oos_acc_df$conf_2.5[row]<-exactci(oos_acc_df$BB_Pos[row], oos_acc_df$total_tested[row], .95)[[1]][1]
```

```
  oos_acc_df$conf_97.5[row]<-exactci(oos_acc_df$BB_Pos[row], oos_acc_df$total_tested[row], .95)[[1]][2]
```

```
  if(oos_acc_df$predictions[row]<=oos_acc_df$conf_97.5[row] & oos_acc_df$predictions[row]>=oos_acc_df$conf_2.5[row]){
```

```
    oos_acc_df$accurate[row]<-1
```

```
  }
```

```
  if(oos_acc_df$predictions[row]>oos_acc_df$conf_97.5[row] | oos_acc_df$predictions[row]<oos_acc_df$conf_2.5[row]){
```

```
    oos_acc_df$accurate[row]<-0
```

```
  }
```

```
}
```

```
#total correct
```

```
sum(oos_acc_df$accurate)
```

```
#incorrect
```

```
length(oos_acc_df$accurate) - sum(oos_acc_df$accurate)
```

```
# percentage correct
```

```
sum(oos_acc_df$accurate) / length(oos_acc_df$accurate)
```

```
#over or under?
```

```
oos_acc_df$inacc<-"A"
```

```
for(row in 1:nrow(oos_acc_df)){
```

```
  if(oos_acc_df$predictions[row] < oos_acc_df$conf_2.5[row]){
```

```
    oos_acc_df$inacc[row]<-"U"
```

```
  }
```

```
  if(oos_acc_df$predictions[row] > oos_acc_df$conf_97.5[row]){
```

```
    oos_acc_df$inacc[row]<- "O"
```

```
  }
```

```
}
```

```
oos_acc_df$new<-temp_test_df$new
```

```
table(oos_acc_df[which(oos_acc_df$new=="yes"), "inacc"])
```

how different was the climate in 2019 compared to 2009-2018?

```

temp_test_df<-test_df[which(test_df$total_tested>10),]
for (var in 1:38){
  temp_stat<-ks.test(train1[m1_Ncoef[var]], temp_test_df[,m1_Ncoef[var]])
  if(temp_stat$statistic>.8){
    temp_p<-ggplot() + geom_density(data=train1, aes(train1[,m1_Ncoef[var]]), fill="blue",alpha=.1) + g
    plot(temp_p)
  }
}

```

6. predictive map prepare for predictive map -don't predict to NYC

```

#areas to keep
ny1<-ny[which(ny$subregion == "main" | ny$subregion == "long island"),]
unique(ny1$subregion)

#NYC counties
ny_county1<-ny_county[which(ny_county$subregion %in% c("bronx", "new york", "queens", "richmond", "king
unique(ny_county1$subregion)

ny_base <- ggplot(data = ny1, mapping = aes(x = long, y = lat, group = group)) +
  coord_fixed(1.3) +
  geom_polygon(color = "white", fill = "white")

ny_baseC <- ggplot(data = ny_county1, mapping = aes(x = long, y = lat, group = group)) +
  coord_fixed(1.3) +
  geom_polygon(color = "white", fill = "white")

gg<-ny_base + theme_nothing(legend = TRUE)
gg

ggC<-ny_baseC + theme_nothing(legend = TRUE)
ggC

plot(ny_base)
plot(ny_baseC)

```

predict to all of NYS (modify code from tick collection models) -use grid of points -use the model to predict pathogen infection to each point -save results to csv (lat, long, predictions), i.e. "map2019_PRED_m1.csv"

make map

```

temp<-fread("/Users/tammy/Box/Research/Project_DIN/predict2019/map2019_PRED_m1.csv")
#categorize infection rates
temp$predictions<-0
temp[which( (temp$pred<=0.10) & (temp$pred>=0)), "predictions"]<-1
temp[which( (temp$pred<=0.20) & (temp$pred>0.10)), "predictions"]<-2
temp[which( (temp$pred<=0.5) & (temp$pred>0.20)), "predictions"]<-3
temp[which( (temp$pred<=1) & (temp$pred>0.5)), "predictions"]<-4
temp<-temp[,c("LONG", "LAT", "predictions")]

gg2 <- gg + geom_raster(data=temp, aes(x = LONG, y = LAT, color = factor(predictions), fill=factor(predi
plot(gg2)

```

```

#number of ticks, sites, counties across all years /sites
sum(df_all$total_tested)
dim(unique(df_all[,c("LAT", "LONG")]))
length(unique(df_all[,c("County")]))

#number of ticks, sites, counties for all training data, 2009-2018
sum(data_df$total_tested)
dim(unique(data_df[,c("LAT", "LONG")]))
length(unique(data_df[,c("County")]))

#number of ticks, sites, counties for training data w/ 10+ ticks
sum(train1ori$total_tested)
dim(train1ori)
dim(unique(train1ori[,c("LAT", "LONG")]))
length(unique(train1ori[,c("County")]))

#number of ticks and sites for 2019
sum(test_df$total_tested)
dim(unique(test_df[,c("LAT", "LONG")]))
length(unique(test_df[,c("County")]))

#number of ticks and sites for 2019 w/ 10+ ticks
sum(test_df$total_tested[which(test_df$total_tested>10)])
dim(unique(test_df[which(test_df$total_tested>10),c("LAT", "LONG")]))
length(unique(test_df[which(test_df$total_tested>10),c("County")]))

#infection rates
summary(df_all[, "prop"])
summary(df_all[which(df_all$total_tested>10), "prop"])
sum(df_all[which(df_all$total_tested>10), "total_tested"])
summary(df_all[which(df_all$total_tested>10), "total_tested"])

#infection % by year
df_all %>% group_by(Year) %>% summarise(median = median(prop))

#relationship between change in rate of infection and rate of ticks
t<-df_all %>% group_by(Year) %>% summarise(median = median(prop), median_tick=median(tarden))
t<-data.frame(t)
a<-c()
b<-c()
for(year in 2:nrow(t)){
  a1<- t$median[year] - t$median[year-1]
  a<-c(a,a1)
  b1<- t$median_tick[year] - t$median_tick[year-1]
  b<-c(b,b1)
}

cor(t$median,t$median_tick)
cor(a,b)

```

7. additional analysis